

RADIO WAVE SURGERY

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ANNOTATION.

Radio wave surgery, one how many diseases in treatment or diagnosis in doing used medical method and radio waves (X -ray of rays) physical structural tools with transition during received from the data uses _ This is the method images and another data get for x-ray of the rays application _ temporarily to deformation meet tools through done is increased . Radio wave of surgery one how many categories available , how type to be used depending , in particular classic radiography and a modern computer with tomography (CT). depends .

Key words: radiography , computer tomography, multidetector tomography

INTRODUCTION

Classic radiography , x- rays application _ own into takes _ X- rays in it from organs passing _ medium show strength (viscosity). reach for is used . This is surgery category in the composition simple x-ray rays (radiography) and fluoroscopy (hidden surgery) categories there is . From radiography , basically in medicine treatment for used x-ray charges through the body internal structures show for is used . This is diagnostic method basically with bone structures , organs , and sized structures confirmation and show in order to is used . Radiography basically cementations , fractures , infections , and another medical circumstances in determining is used . Radiography , from roentgen rays using and them inside the body to structures take enters _ X-ray of the rays energy different structures by acceptance will be done and this contrast digital detector through to the image get for is used . Radiography , medical in diagnosis very big important have are breasts , organs , and _ structures in determining is used . From radiography came out images to see x- charge for devices is used . This device is an x-ray from the pipe and from the detector consists of will be Doctor by this device X-ray the patient detector and lamp between will be placed , that's it with x-ray image is taken .

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

X-ray in the rays images digital detectors through is taken , this while image fast and comfortable get enable will give . Radiography ionized possible in

roentgen rays devices uses , but their power high that it was for , in radiography in the x- rays used the dose minimize for safety measures done increase very important _ Conventional radiography when used , tomography (CT), magnet resonance imaging (MRI), ultrasound and another image to see There are also methods . Each of them their own advantages and medical types in showing used. Radiography , in medicine important diagnostic method as works and the situation in detection and treatment and in observation to doctors help give in getting big role plays _

Computer Tomography (CT) and x -ray of the rays application _ with together applied diagnostic is a method . This surgery series , computer tomograph 3D imaging using a CT scanner and big anatomical structural of means information When received , it is also large fast and sure images in getting is used . Computer tomography organs , neck _ and another anatomical data in getting amenities creates _ This is surgery series , unexpected anatomical structural parts show , diseases _ diagnosis do , and treatment mode inchoosing used. Radio wave surgery , many diseases diagnosis in making , another diagnostic methods with combined without , bright and transparent images in getting useful in medicine _ being used the most famous diagnostic from tools is one

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

X-ray rays ionization for intended _ _ it will be _ _ while molecules with effect _ _ and chemical o ' changes brings _ Health for , used rays dose very is important and different methods with to be compared need _

Radio wave surgery for used rays , harmful development effect to do can _ These are the rules of DNA broke to send and in the body different o' changes to bring can _ Radiography and for CT used rays , disease diagnosis to do and in treatment very strong and useful if they are _ physical and structural changes take coming can _ And this ill indicators in understanding help gives , but radiation external the temperature to increase can _ Radio wave in surgery used tools , right and reliable work output , employees and the sick for very comfortable and use easy has been methods to be need _ Radiography and KT, one how much diseases diagnosis to do and another diagnostic tools with combined without , main diagnostic from tools one good health _ _ in storage very good results in getting help gives. These with together with radio waves of surgery diagnostic the results in getting very important has been thing , sick people health storage for dose control to be done and of employees safe work methods with depends . In use rays dose very strong and in use tools right potential if not controlled danger , physical changes _ and radiation damages

take coming can _ Therefore , radio waves _ of surgery very reliable and attention with use need. Computer tomography (CT) in medicine physical organs and structure 3D image of parts in getting used bright is a diagnostic method. CT scan using received tomograms , large structural tools , processes , and anatomical structure of parts features more precisely shows _ _ CT, one how many important effect and advantages have _ CT scan , physical structural tools and processes more precisely in describing and bright anatomical images in getting very strong will be _ This is health in storage , the disease diagnosis in doing and in treatment very good results in getting help gives.KT , developing diagnostic tools in , security in providing will be an assistant . It is of roentgen rays application _ for recommendation done in doses works and modern tools with when compared very less radiation effect harvest does _ Computer tomography fast it helps in obtaining results and is used by the radiologist to understand the patient's condition more quickly. MDCT, one how many detectors more experienced results in getting help will give . This method is one how many layered images fast get and modern diagnosis opportunities to increase possibility will give . CT, wide anatomical fields and changes _ in showing help will give . It is on the surface did not come out diseases , structural changes _ in determining good results in getting amenities creates.CBCT , complex structured represents a layered tomography that is very useful for fields such as dentistry , neurosurgery and other fields. Angiography for used computer tomography (CT angiography) blood of flow features more precisely shows and sure images in getting help will give . This is blood flow anatomy circumstances diagnosis in doing and treatment mode in choosing used.Computer tomography , health storage and diseases diagnosis in doing important important have has been the most modern diagnostic from tools It is a method processes , characteristic changes _ and surface did not come out diseases in understanding certain has been helper being doctors _ and radiologists for is used .

Conclusion .

Computer tomography (CT or CT scan) medical diagnosis for used is a method . In this method, the roentgen rays sharp image get for computer and detectors is used . Computer tomography one how many advantages available : CT scans internal of organs , structures , and inside the body another of structures bright and right image in getting very big practical to brightness have _ This is medical indicators determination and diagnosis in putting very useful will be CT, one how many tissue united images get enable will give . These images the diagnosis

to determine more makes it easier . CT scans, internal structures closer analysis to do and this structures manage for contrast substances to add enable will give . This is different different diagnoses for big opportunities Creates CT , rounding of organs (for example , liver) . and mobile It is also very useful in determining diagnoses (for example , liver) . useful. This to doctors that's it to act in terms of the following treatment methods to develop or operations done to increase road in putting help gives.CT scanners fast the results get enable gives , this while to doctors and to the users fast and complete info to give possibility will give . CT imaging charge as works , but this number is too much less at the level of , therefore for Dangerous the fact that is less . This is the following treatment processes for service to do for good method will be.Computer tomography , medical in diagnosis wide applied practitioner and comfortable method is different _ different diagnoses in getting high level help will give .

Used books:

1. Boboqulova, M. X. (2023). STOMATOLOGIK MATERIALLARNING FIZIK-MEXANIK XOSSALARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(9), 223-228.
2. Xamroyevna, B. M. (2023). ORGANIZM TO 'QIMALARINING ZICHLIGINI ANIQLASH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 50-58.
3. Khamroyevna, M. B. (2023). PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF BIOLOGICAL MEMBRANES, BIOPHYSICAL MECHANISMS OF MOVEMENT OF SUBSTANCES IN THE MEMBRANE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 217-221.
4. Bobokulova, M. K. (2023). IMPORTANCE OF FIBER OPTIC DEVICES IN MEDICINE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 212-216.
5. Mukhtaram Bobokulova Khamroyevna. (2023). Radiation Protection. Dosimetry . Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science, 4(6), 134-139.
6. Bobokulova, M. K. (2024). TOLALI OPTIKA ASBOBLARINING TIBBIYOTDAGI AHAMIYATI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 517-524.
7. Axmedova, Z. I. (2023). LMS TIZIMIDA INTERAKTIV ELEMENTLARNI YARATISH TEXNOLOGIYASI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(11), 368-372.
8. Axmedova, Z. (2023). MOODLE TIZIMI VA UNING IMKONIYATLARI. Development and innovations in science, 2(11), 29-35.
9. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). USING THE USEFUL ASPECTS OF THE MOODLE SYSTEM AND ITS POSSIBILITIES. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 201-205.

10. Zulxumor, A. (2022). IMPLEMENTATION OF INTERACTIVE COURSES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. *ILMIY TADQIQOT VA INNOVATSIYA*, 1(6), 128-132.
11. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). SQL (STRUCTURED QUERY LANGUAGE) STATISTICAL PACKAGES OF CAPABILITIES. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 2(12), 781-787.
12. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). SQL (STRUCTURED QUERY LANGUAGE) CAPABILITIES OF THE STATISTICAL DATABASE LANGUAGE. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 3(5), 274-280.
13. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). CREATION AND PLACEMENT OF INTERACTIVE ELEMENTS. *Solution of social problems in management and economy*, 2(13), 120-128.
14. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS, ELECTRONIC EDUCATION: TASKS AND OPPORTUNITIES. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 2(21), 171-177.
15. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). DISADVANTAGES OF ELECTRONIC LEARNING. *Current approaches and new research in modern sciences*, 2(12), 99-109.
16. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). SQL SPECIFICATIONS FOR DATA ANALYSIS. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 2(13), 113-120.
17. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). Programming Environments for Creating Mobile Applications on the Android Operating System. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(10), 305-309.
18. Latipova, S. S. qizi . (2024). CAPUTO MA'NOSIDAGI KASR TARTIBLI TENGLAMALARDA MANBA FUNKSIYANI ANIQLASH BO'YICHA TO'G'RI MASALALAR. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 2(1), 375-382.
19. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). BETA FUNKSIYA XOSSALARI VA BU FUNKSIYA YORDAMIDA TURLI MASALALARNI YECHISH. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(34), 66-76.
20. Latipova, S. S. qizi . (2024). KASR TARTIBLI ODDIY DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMALAR. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 2(1), 383-390.
21. Latipova, S. S. qizi . (2024). GAMMA FUNKSIYA. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 2(1), 391-399.
22. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). SOLVING THE INVERSE PROBLEM OF FINDING THE SOURCE FUNCTION IN FRACTIONAL ORDER EQUATIONS. *International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development*, 10(12).
23. Latipova, S. S. (2023). SOLVING THE INVERSE PROBLEM OF FINDING THE SOURCE FUNCTION IN FRACTIONAL ORDER EQUATIONS. *Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal*, 1(10), 13-23.

24. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). HEAT PHYSICAL MEANING AND ORIGIN OF DIFFUSION EQUATIONS. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).
25. daughter Latipova, S. S. (2023). HEAT PHYSICAL MEANING AND ORIGIN OF DIFFUSION EQUATIONS. World of Scientific news in Science, 1(2), 163-176.
26. Shahnoza, L. (2023, March). KASR TARTIBLI TENGLAMALARDA MANBA VA BOSHLANG'ICH FUNKSIYANI ANIQLASH BO'YICHA TESKARI MASALALAR. In "Conference on Universal Science Research 2023" (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 8-10).
27. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). RIMAN-LUIVILL KASR TARTIBLI INTEGRALI VA HOSILASIGA OID AYRIM MASALALARNING ISHLANISHI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(12), 216-220.
28. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). MITTAG-LIFFLER FUNKSIYASI VA UNI HISOBLASH USULLARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(9), 238-244.
29. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). KASR TARTIBLI HOSILA TUSHUNCHASI. SCHOLAR, 1(31), 263-269.
30. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). Zamonaviy ta'limda axborot texnologiyalari va ularni qo'llash usul va vositalari. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(11), 481-486.
31. Муродов, О. Т. (2023). РАЗРАБОТКА АВТОМАТИЗИРОВАННОЙ СИСТЕМЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ТЕМПЕРАТУРЫ И ВЛАЖНОСТИ В ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕННЫХ КОМНАТ. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(26), 91-95.
32. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). INFORMATIKA DARSLARINI TASHKIL ETISHDA INNOVATSION USULLARDAN FOYDALANISH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(32), 194-201.
33. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). INFORMATIKA FANINI O'QITISHDA YANGI INNOVATSION USULLARDAN FOYDALANISH METODIKASI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 130-139.
34. MURODOV, O. T. (2023). INNOVATIVE INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES AND NEW METHODS AND TOOLS FOR THEIR APPLICATION IN TODAY'S EDUCATION. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).
35. Turakulovich, M. O. (2023). DEVELOPMENT AND INSTALLATION OF AN AUTOMATIC TEMPERATURE CONTROL SYSTEM IN ROOMS. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).
36. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g, Q. li.(2023). Mobil ilovalar yaratish va ularni bajarish jarayoni. International journal of scientific researchers, 2(2).

37. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g, Q. (2023). USE OF ARTIFICIAL NERVOUS SYSTEMS IN MODELING. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 269-273.
38. Behruz Ulugbek og, Q. (2023). TECHNOLOGY AND MEDICINE: A DYNAMIC PARTNERSHIP. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(11).
39. Quvvatov, B. U. o'g'li . (2023). ALEXNET - TASVIRLARNI TASNIFLASH UCHUN KONVOLYUTSION NEYRON TARMOQ. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 77–90.
- 40.
41. Sharipova, M. P. L. (2023). CAPUTA MA'NOSIDA KASR TARTIBLI HOSILALAR VA UNI HISOBLASH USULLARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(9), 360-365.
42. Sharipova, M. P. (2023). MAXSUS SOHALARDA KARLEMAN MATRITSASI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(10), 137-141.
43. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). APPROXIMATION OF FUNCTIONS WITH COEFFICIENTS. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 135–138.
44. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). Applications of the double integral to mechanical problems. International journal of sciearchers, 2(2), 101-103.
45. Sharipova, M. P. L. (2023). FINDING THE MAXIMUM AND MINIMUM VALUE OF A FUNCTION ON A SEGMENT. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 245-248.
46. Sharipova, M. P. (2023). FUNKSIYALARNI KOEFFITSIENTLAR ORQALI FUNKSIYALARNI YAKINLASHTIRISH HAQIDA MA'LUMOTLAR. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 102–110.
47. Sharipova, M. (2023, December). RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN STRAIGHT LINES AND PLANES IN SPACE. In Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 2, No. 12, pp. 60-66).
48. Sharipova, M. (2023). FRACTIONAL DERIVATIVES. Академические исследования в современной науке, 2(27), 106-113.
49. Sharipova, M. (2023). CORRECT PLACED AND CORRECT NOT PLACED ISSUES. Models and methods in modern science, 2(13), 115-121.
50. Sharipova, M. (2023). HEAT SPREAD EQUATION. Инновационные исследования в науке, 2(12), 50-56.
51. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). HIGH MATH SCORE AND INTERVAL ASSESSMENT. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 420–424.

52. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). IN HIGHER MATHEMATICS, THE EXTREMUM OF A MULTIVARIABLE FUNCTION. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 425–429.
53. Sharipova, M. P. (2024). ISSIQLIK TARQALISH TENGLAMASI UCHUN KOSHI MASALASI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 525–532.
54. qizi Sharopova, M. M. (2023). Working with folders in the JAVA programming language. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 232-236.
55. qizi Sharopova, M. M. (2023). INTRODUCING "PROGRAM CONTROL OPERATORS" IN THE JAVA PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 222-231.
56. Sharopova, M. (2023). ARRAY AND ARRAYS INSTALLATION. Development of pedagogical technologies in modern sciences, 2(12), 102-107.
57. Sharopova, M. (2023). JAVA PROGRAMMING IN THE LANGUAGE HERITAGE TO DO SYNTAX. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 2(12), 82-87.
58. Sharopova, M. (2023). CHOOSE: COMPOSITION OR INHERITANCE. Science and innovation in the education system, 2(13), 96-102.
59. qizi Sharopova, M. M. (2023). JAVA TILI YORDAMIDA OB'EKTGA YUNALTIRILGAN DASTURLASH ASOSLARI BILAN TANISHISH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 111-119.
60. Muxayyo Muxtor qizi Sharopova. (2023). INTRODUCING "PROGRAM CONTROL OPERATORS" IN THE JAVA PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 222–231.
61. Muxayyo Muxtor qizi Sharopova. (2023). Working with folders in the JAVA programming language. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 232–236.
62. Sharopova, M. (2024). DSA ERI STANDARD. ELECTRONIC DIGITAL SIGNATURE OF GOST R 34.10-94. В THEORETICAL ASPECTS IN THE FORMATION OF PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 169–178).
63. Sharopova, M. (2024). ELECTRONIC DIGITAL SIGNATURE ALGORITHMS BASED ON THE COMPLEXITY OF THE FACTORIZATION PROBLEM. В SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 66–74).
64. Sharopova, M. (2024). ARRAYS AND ARRAYS INSTALLATION. В CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 102–110).

65. Sharopova, M. (2024). JAVA PROGRAMMING IN THE LANGUAGE FLOWING INPUT AND RELEASE. В SOLUTION OF SOCIAL PROBLEMS IN MANAGEMENT AND ECONOMY (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 84–93).
66. Sharopova, M. (2024). COLLECTORS. (OBJECT CONTAINERS). В DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN MODERN SCIENCES (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 93–101).
67. Murodov, O. (2024). DEVELOPMENT OF AN AUTOMATED SYSTEM FOR CONTROLLING TEMPERATURE AND HUMIDITY IN PRODUCTION ROOMS. В DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATIONS IN SCIENCE (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 84–93).
68. Murodov, O. (2024). DEVELOPMENT OF AN AUTOMATED PARAMETER CONTROL SYSTEM ROOMS AND WORKSHOPS BASED ON CLOUD TECHNOLOGIES. В ACADEMIC RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCE (Т. 3, Выпуск 2, сс. 16–27).
69. Muradov, O. (2024). BASIC PRINCIPLES AND RULES OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. В MODELS AND METHODS IN MODERN SCIENCE (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 84–93).
70. Muradov, O. (2024). APPLIED TO THE CURRENT TRAINING PROCESS REQUIREMENTS. В INNOVATIVE RESEARCH IN SCIENCE (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 54–63).
71. Muradov, O. (2024). APPLICATION OF BASIC PRINCIPLES AND RULES OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES TO EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES. В МЕЖДУРОДНАЯ КОНФЕРЕНЦИЯ АКАДЕМИЧЕСКИХ НАУК (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 46–55).
72. Tursunov, B. J., & Allanazarov, G. O. (2019). Perspektivnye tehnologii proizvodstva po uluchsheniyu kachestva benzina. Theory and practice of contemporary science, 3(45), 305-308.
73. Турсунов, Б. Ж., & Алланазаров, Г. О. (2019). Перспективные технологии производства по улучшению качества бензина. Теория и практика современной науки, (3 (45)), 305-308.
74. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). Analysis of Concepts About the Effect of an Explosion in Solid Wednesday. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 296-304.
75. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). Methods of Control of Explosion Energy Distribution in Rocks. Intersections of Faith and Culture: American Journal of Religious and Cultural Studies (2993-2599), 1(10), 108-117.

76. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). WASTE-FREE TECHNOLOGY FOR ENRICHMENT OF PURIFIC COPPER-ZINC ORE. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 288-293.
77. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). ANALYSIS OF MODERN METHODS FOR OIL SLUDGE PROCESSING. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 280-287.
78. Jumaev, K., & Tursunov, B. (2022, December). Environmentally friendly technology for obtaining fuel briquettes from oil waste. In IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science (Vol. 1112, No. 1, p. 012005). IOP Publishing.
79. Ахмедова, О. Б., Турсунов, Б. Ж., & угли Худойбердиев, Н. Н. (2022). Анализ физико-химических свойств нефтешламов Бухарского НПЗ и рациональные способы их утилизации. Science and Education, 3(6), 495-507.
80. Турсунов, Б. Д. (2016). Анализ и выявление путей совершенствования процессов горного дела. Молодой ученый, (23), 105-106.
81. Jurakulov, S. Z. O., & Nurboyev, O. (2023). THE MAIN SIGNIFICANCE OF THE DEPARTMENTS OF PHYSICS IN THE DEVELOPMENT. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 162-167.
82. Jurakulov, S. Z. O., & Turdiboyev, H. (2023). RELATIONSHIPS OF PHYSICS WITH ART IN THE FIELD OF EDUCATION. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 144-147.
83. Jurakulov, S. Z. O., & Turdiboyev, H. (2023). ADVANCED STRATEGIES FOR LEARNING PHYSICS. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 152-156.
84. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Nurboyev, O. (2023). IN THE EDUCATIONAL FIELD OF PHYSICS LEVEL AND POSITION. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 157-161.
85. Jurakulov, S. (2023). PROPERTIES AND CHARACTERISTICS OF NUCLEAR ENERGY. Инновационные исследования в науке, 2(12), 35-39.
86. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Hamidov, E. (2023). YADRO ENERGIYASINING XOSSA VA XUSUSIYATLARI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 182-186.
87. IN THE EDUCATIONAL FIELD OF PHYSICS LEVEL AND POSITION
88. SZ Jurakulov, O Nurboyev - GOLDEN BRAIN, 2023
89. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Turdiboyev, X. (2023). FIZIKA FANINI O 'RGANISHNING YUQORI DARAJADAGI STRATEGIYALAR. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 152-156.
90. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Turdiboyev, X. (2023). TA'LIM SOHASIDA FIZIKANING SAN'AT BILAN ALOQALARI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 144-147.
91. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Nurboyev, O. (2023). FIZIKA FANINING BO 'LIMLARINING RIVOJLANISHDAGIDAGI ASOSIY AHAMIYATI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 162-167.

92. Jurakulov, S. (2023). ON THE RELATION OF METAPHYSICS TO PHYSICS. Академические исследования в современной науке, 2(27), 9-20.
93. Jurakulov, S. (2023). ON THE RELATION OF METAPHYSICS TO PHYSICS. Академические исследования в современной науке, 2(27), 9-20.
94. Jurakulov, S. (2023). IMPACT OF THE MINING INDUSTRY ON PEOPLE AND THE ENVIRONMENT. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 2(21), 143-150.
95. Jurakulov, S. (2023). CHANGES IN LANGUAGE DUE TO NEW PHYSICS. Models and methods in modern science, 2(13), 77-87.
96. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). СОЗДАНИЕ ПРОГРАММЫ ДЛЯ ИМИТАЦИИ ШИФРОВАНИЯ МАШИНЫ ENIGMA НА ЯЗЫКЕ PYTHON. TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN, 1(5), 317-323.
97. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). STUDY THE PSYCHOLOGY OF PROGRAMMERS. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 563-568.